

Problems of the Study of Oikonyms in Multi-System Languages

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Abstract. *This article discusses the problems of the study of oikonyms in various languages. The idea is substantiated that the character of oikonyms is influenced by the structure of the language, its imagery, grammatical structure, interaction with other languages, as well as the natural environment in which native speakers live. The style of thinking, perception of the world through images and representations are reflected in the names of the geographical environment, their preservation and use in everyday life, as well as in artistic practice. The use of oikonyms, their transfer from one language to another, and the nature of the distortions that manifest themselves depend on the group and language family to which they belong.*

Key words: *oikonyms, multi-system languages, the study of oikonyms, grammatical structure, perception of the world.*

It is known that the knowledge of oikonyms, their preservation and strengthening on the geographical map contributes to the formation of a special mentality closely related to the native language, the area of its application, the concepts that are reflected in it, as well as those that are in its immediate social and natural environment. Let us immediately emphasize that the issues of oikonymy are especially actively studied in languages with a large number of native speakers and constantly replenishing active systems. That is why we turned to multi-system languages, that is, to languages belonging to the agglutinative and inflectional systems of word composition - these are Uzbek, Russian and English. The long-term practice of researching oikonyms has pursued several goals: as a means of determining the location, as a historical reference to the ethnic and demographic processes that once took place in this territory, as a means of expressiveness of speech, strengthening the content and intonation components in oral, written, artistic and other types of speech.

The main quality and purpose of oikonymy in any language is to determine the nature of space, its features in order to separate it into a separate representation and for memorization, for subsequent communication. This can be judged by the work of such famous researchers as V.I. Dahl, V.A.Nikonov, A.V.Superanskaya, L.V.Uspensky, A.A.Reformatsky, as well as K.M. Veremieva, I.G.Koshevaya, O.V.Lagutina and others. [1].

The peculiarities of terminology in oikonymy are their mobility and variability. Names associated with ethnic, political, and national characteristics are particularly subject to numerous changes. The main thing for a linguist is to study the process of transformation of a concept into a word, historical and ethnographic features of the development of concepts according to oikonymy. [3]

A number of specialized journals on oikonymy are published in Russia. The applied aspects of regional peculiarities of processes in oikonymy are mainly studied here. In the research of Russian scientists, much attention is paid to the problem of the functioning of the oikonym in language and speech, as well as the problem of the meaning of the oikonym in various contexts. The component analysis of the meaning of oikonyms was carried out by a number of researchers such as N.K.Itchenko, N.L.Kolmakova, V.D. Pakhomova, S.M.Perkas and others. [4]

V.A.Nikonov, A.V.Superanskaya, V.D.Belenkaya, K.M.Irskhanova and others have confirmed with their research the fact that the meaning of the oikonym correlates with its function, which it performs in language and speech. According to the concepts put forward by V.A.Nikonov and V.D.Belenka, the oikonym has three planes of meaning: pre-understanding (etymological), toponymic (specific, named) and post-toponymic (otonomnic). [6] The oikonym, used in speech in a figurative sense, performs several functions (except nominative): characterizing, symbolic and allusive. Figurative (metaphorical and metonymic) use of the oikonym is possible due to the ottonymic plan of the meaning of the oikonym. [2] It should be noted that toponymic appellatives semantically represent a peculiar and semantically limited group of words. The study of the process of formation of toponymic vocabulary in a historical perspective indicates that the phenomenon present in the language at different stages of its development is quite fully manifested and remains active at the present time.

Today, people's geographical representations are expanding, as a result, knowledge about the oikonymy of a particular region, resort, historical area is increasing many times. In general, "the human factor is decisive both in the figurative characterization and assessment of a topoobject, and in the figurative characterization and assessment of an object or phenomenon of reality expressed by an oikonym." Russian researcher I.A. Kondakova, based on a large amount of factual material, considered the use of oikonyms in figurative expressions, and not only in fiction. [6] We believe that this is an interesting and promising area of research on the application and use of oikonyms in the language. In this sense, research on onomastics, of which oikonymy is an integral part, is of great interest. In particular, an analysis of phraseological turns and stable phrases in the Uzbek language, where oikonyms would be used, would be of interest. So far, there are collections of folk proverbs, sayings, sayings, tongue twisters, published on the basis of the collected material by Uzbek researchers, which also reflect the oikonymy of the region, region or locality. Among them are the works of K.Alieva, V.Veliyeva and others. [1]

Sociolinguistics issues are of great importance in the study of linguistic processes, including in the field of oikonymy. The area of the language, the ethnic history and politics of the people – its native speaker, socio-economic and spiritual and moral life are reflected in the use of oikonyms, their semantic content, and so on. I. Bayramov writes about this convincingly in his work. [5]

If, in general, language processes are an important part of the language policy of each country, then special attention is paid to that section of it that is associated with the assignment of historical names to a particular locality or geographical object. This is due to national identification, political self-determination, self-awareness of the people, their literature, and spiritual life in general. That is why the government of each country is attentive to the territorial and administrative division of the country, their names. It sometimes happens that the old names of cities and villages are restored. It was in this direction that work was carried out in the countries of the post-Soviet space.

Work on oikonyms, as already mentioned, went in several directions, and continues to this day: such sciences as history, geography, ethnography, linguistics, and literary studies are engaged in them. There are areas in the country's language policy that are related to oikonymy. The history, theory of linguistics and literary criticism is associated with such areas of research on the problems of oikonymy as the semantic content of terms, their stylistic variability, the history of formation and development.

A separate area of research in this area is the use of oikonyms in artistic speech. This refers to both oral folk art and the professional work of writers and poets. It should be noted that few separate studies have been conducted in the Azerbaijani philological science in this direction. There are no studies on the comparative study of the use of oikonyms in fiction in diverse languages. This is quite an interesting direction in science, since it makes it possible to take a deeper look at the linguistic processes taking place in connection with the use of oikonyms in various languages. Here it is necessary to proceed from the linguistic characteristics, style of thinking, lifestyle, geographical features of the area where a native speaker lives, i.e. a particular people, as well as socio-political and spiritual and moral processes in their historical development.

Oikonymy is an important direction in the development of linguistics in the modern period. This is evidenced by the huge literature that has been formed over the last century in diverse languages. The importance of the work being carried out is determined by the role that oikonyms play in human life and in society as a whole. This is a problem of "recognizing" oneself, identification, and, above all, national self-identification. Consequently, the work of a philologist, geographer, historian, sociologist, psychologist is aimed at preserving historical memory, forming stereotypes of thinking related to self-determination and self-awareness of each member of society.

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